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Social and Economic Systems of Society: Concept, Objectives, Trends

У статті розкрито проблематику розвитку економічної та соціальної систем суспільства з позицій науки теорії держави і права. Наголошено, що сьогодні як міжнародна спільнота, так і українське суспільство в активному пошуку більш ефективних моделей соціальної та економічної систем. Підкреслено, що новітні тенденції зумовлюють здійснити інноваційно-структурну перебудову вітчизняної економічної системи суспільства. Зроблено висновок, що розвиток духовно-культурної та політичної сфер сьогодні все більше стикається з проблемою уповільнення формування відкритої економічної системи. Визначено напрями оновлення економічної системи суспільства.

Ключові слова: економічна система суспільства, соціальна система суспільства, кібереконіміка, модернізація, децентралізація.

В статье раскрыто проблематику развития экономической и социальной систем общества с позиций науки теории государства и права. Отмечено, что сегодня как международное сообщество, так и украинское общество в активном поиске более эффективных моделей социальной и экономической систем. Подчеркнуто, что новейшие тенденции обуславливают осуществит инновационно-структурную перестройку отечественной экономической системы общества. Сделан вывод, что развитие духовно-культурной и политической сфер сегодня все больше сталкивается с проблемой замедления формирования открытой экономической системы. Определены направления обновления экономической системы общества.

Ключевые слова: экономическая система общества, социальная система общества, киберэкономика, модернизация, децентрализация.

The article reveals the problems of the development of the economic and social systems of society of the science of the theory of state and law. It is stressed that today, both the international community and Ukrainian society are actively seeking more effective models of social and economic systems. It is emphasised that the latest trends make it possible to carry out an innovation restructuring of the domestic economic system of society, since today the lack of the specified significantly weakens the position of Ukraine and suspends its integration. It is concluded that the development of spiritual, cultural and political spheres today increasingly faces the problem of the delay in the formation of an open economic system. It is highlighted that modern economic and social systems of society are complex formations; the definition of concepts “economic system of society” and “social system of society” are formulated.

Ensuring the citizens of Ukraine with the opportunity to fully implement economic and social rights requires the renewal of the economic system of society in the following areas: active introduction of innovative technologies; cooperation and attraction of international investors; promotion of the peoples creative potential; maximum supply of goods by the national market; transition to a system of export of end-use goods, not raw materials; balance of economic freedom; providing high-quality service. Their implementation requires the reform of domestic legislation, the detailed elaboration of a national mechanism for achieving this, with the

involvement of representatives of Ukrainian and foreign business. The directions of the modernization of the economic system of the society, which will help ensure the citizens of Ukraine with the opportunity to fully implement economic and social rights, are determined.

Keywords: *economic systems of society, social systems of society, cybereconomy, modernization, decentralization.*

Problem statement. Having declared the democratic vector of development and striving to enter the world community as an equal partner, Ukraine must meet the high demands of the present in both political, and social and economic aspects. Despite the powerful domestic human, economic, humanitarian and cultural potential, Ukrainian state failed to realize its obvious advantages, to create a social and economic theory of development that would correlate with the present reality.

The formation of an open society in our country coincides with the development of the economic system of society. Contrary to the complexities and contradictions of the transition period, Ukraine is slowly strengthening as a rule of law, accelerating its integration into the world economic space. However, the processes associated with globalization predetermine the complexity of the task with regard to the previous stage. The problem of developing the economic system of society is one of the key and most theoretically significant for modern legal science and the development of civil society and the formation of a legal, social state in Ukraine.

The study of this problem has not only theoretical, but also important practical importance for the effective development of all spheres of society.

Analysis of Publications. Some of the problematic issues of the formation of the economic system were studied in the writings of such scholars as O. Borysova, O. Bieliaieva, I. Grabynskyi, Z. Zalogy, V. Iokhina, M. Krupky, B. Kulchytskyi, R. Kuchukova, S. Liubymtseva, O. Mamontova, I. Myhasiuka, S. Mochernyi, L. Nalyvaiko, P. Ostroverha, S. Panchyshyna, S. Pogorielova, V. Popova, D. Potieieva, S. Reverchuk, D. Stechenko, O. Tyshchenko, V. Fomishchena, T. Shkliar and other scientists. However, the rapid pace of world economic development and the need to integrate Ukraine into these processes in order to effectively develop the modern social system require new scientific research in this field, in particular from the standpoint of science in the theory of state and law.

Presenting main material. Comprehensive study of the social and economic systems of society requires the disclosure of their content primarily at the categorical rather than everyday level.

Fundamental theoretical and practical contribution to the development of the social system was carried out in his time by B. Havrylyshyn. The scientist considered the economic system as an element in the architecture of the social structure, which itself is a certain system and includes the relevant elements: values (beliefs that affect relationships between individuals or groups, relations within society), political governance (a set of political institutions and procedures), an economic system (a way of organizing the production and distribution of wealth created in society). Values, in his opinion, can be individualist-competitive, group-cooperative, egalitarian-collectivist. The values of society and the forms of political rule determine the main prototypes of economic systems, the scientist identified three of them: the economic system of free enterprise (there prevails the private property, free market, the desire to maximize profits – all that is approved by legislative acts and creates a rival relationship between the government, entrepreneurs, employees), the economic system of a coordinated free enterprise (similar to the previous one, but with the possibility to reach agreement on national priorities, co-ordination of the government, entrepreneurs, and employees' economic efforts to make it more efficient and more humane), the administrative-command economic system (characterized by state or collective ownership, maximization of production, a totally disorganized market, the decisive role of the government in addressing economic issues through central planning and administrative allocation of resources) [1, c. 21-29]. This classification is based on the characterization of economic systems on five grounds: the main motive or criterion of activity (maximizing profit or production, viability), the nature of ownership (private, state, collective), the nature of the market (free, regulated, controlled), the role of the state in the economic system, the root cause and the main goal (economic, social, political)

[2]. The proposed authors vision of the economic system of society as a component of the social structure does not lose its relevance to the international community as a whole and Ukrainian society in particular to this day.

We emphasise that any study is based, first of all, on the refinement of the main categories used in scientific work. Therefore, the study of the question of the development of social and economic systems of society as elements of the modern social structure requires their terminological concretization. This issue is even more actualized in connection with the different theoretical constructs used by scientists in their research. In particular, some scientists believe that it is expedient and methodologically correct to use the terms economic system of society and social system of society separately, while others are proponents of the theory of the term socio-economic system of society. A detailed review of author's approaches to this issue is necessary.

Speaking as a supporter of the use of the concept of socio-economic system, K. Moiseienko substantiates his position as follows: the social nature of the coexistence of people in the course of meeting their needs and its creation – morality, law, and so on – determines the unity of social and economic aspects in the economic system, therefore and the need to use the concept of socio-economic system more objectively refers to a set of relationships between people for the realization of their interests to meet the needs [3, c. 33]. We believe that such an author's position is not an objective justification of the expediency of combining these phenomena into a single system, yet despite their meaningful proximity. These systems are more likely to be complementary; they still require independent elements of the modern social structure.

In the economic, political, legal, and other literature, a number of definitions of the notion economic system of society are formulated:

a set of interconnected and properly organized productive forces, economic relations and a mechanism of management, the main function of which is to ensure the dynamic balance in social production, first of all, between consumption and production, demand and supply [4, c. 119]; a concrete historical model of the socio-economic mode of production that represents the unity of productive forces and industrial relations under the influence of factors of the superstructure (economic structures and their relations, level of coordination

and production management, national customs, cultural traditions, etc.) [5, c. 63]; a set of political, social and economic institutions, organizations, laws, norms, rules and beliefs that interact directly or indirectly, affecting consumption, distribution, exchange and production [6, c. 29]; the socioeconomic system of society is a hierarchical, integrative, open, adaptive, dynamic, fractal, nonlinear, integral set of organized socio-economic relations of people about meeting their needs and ensuring a common existence in conditions of relatively limited resources and certain social space in the labour process or implementation of other forms of motivated individual and social behavior [3, c. 34; 7, c. 261]. Taking into account existing interpretations of the concepts of the economic system of society and the social system of society, modern democratic processes and globalization peculiarities, it is appropriate to define these concepts as follows. The economic system of society is a coherent, normative and institutionalized interaction of various elements of economic activity aimed at the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of tangible and intangible goods, services, profit making in order to meet the needs and interests of people. The social system of society is defined as a coherent, complex and orderly interaction of social associations and individual entities of a general and specific nature.

It should be noted that for a long time the main forms of ownership were state (nationwide), collective-cooperative, as well as property of trade unions and other public organizations. Therefore, the ownership of the means of production in the form of the state (national) and collective-cooperative was the basis of the economic system of the former USSR and the Ukrainian SSR, and all individual property was considered, paradoxically, derived from the main forms of property, that is, a secondary form of ownership. In addition, it should be noted that economic activity was predominantly social in nature, and the most complete satisfaction of the growing material and spiritual goods of people was formally considered the highest goal of social production [8, c. 23]. In contrast to the aforementioned, today according to the provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine, the property of the Ukrainian people is a priority form of ownership. In particular, Article 13 of the Constitution of Ukraine states that the land, its subsoil, atmospheric air, water and other natural resources located within the

territory of Ukraine, the natural resources of its continental shelf, and the exclusive (marine) economic zone are objects of the property rights of the Ukrainian people. On their behalf, the right of the owner is exercised by the state authorities and local self-government bodies within the limits established by the current Constitution of Ukraine (Article 13). Ownership is one of the main components of the formation and functioning of any society and state.

At the current stage, the active involvement of civil society institutions in improving the functioning of the social and political systems of society is important.

Thus, in Ukraine, taking into account the experience of public self-organization in the last year, sufficient prerequisites have been formed to attract civil society resource potential to the process of guaranteeing social security, in particular a wide network of civil society institutions (associations of citizens, volunteer movements), which include, for example, highly skilled specialists in those or other industries. The support of the public sector by businesses and citizens is also growing [9, c. 392-393]. Participation and interaction of the society with public authorities has a positive effect on the development of social and economic spheres.

At present, a separate, fundamental component of the economic and social systems of society as elements of the modern social structure is the formation of socially-oriented business.

The formation of a market economy must be correlated with the real political, spiritual, cultural, psychological, social and economic conditions prevailing in the country, on the basis of which only it is possible to adapt one or another general theoretical model to real socio-economic activity [4, c. 744; 10, c. 94].

Only within a dynamic civil society business as a social institution acquires the degree of freedom that most fully satisfies the economic, socio-cultural and political needs of entrepreneurs in realizing business potential in the direction of developing effective and mutually beneficial socio-economic relations. Being one of the main subsystems of society, business is understood as a specific institutional complex for each community. One of the basic factors behind business genesis is the ownership system. Today, civil society emancipates Ukrainian business and removes its dependence on non-governmental institutions and groups of influence, provides consolidation and stability of

civil society, minimizes social risks and shocks in the future and promotes prestige of business as a socially significant component of the present [11, c. 14]. Support and development of business in Ukraine is the basis of its further development, as it will contribute to the improvement of the economic situation of citizens. It is also important that the protection of business in our state is a guarantee of attracting foreign investments to Ukraine.

In the conditions of the development of the information society, the issue of establishing an e-economy and e-business as an integral part of it becomes more and more relevant. E-business is aimed, first of all, at objectively meeting the interests and needs of the public.

Electronic economy is an economic activity based on information technologies, one aspect of which is the management of e-business (online business), electronic money, e-commerce, e-bank, etc. [12, c. 50]. At the present stage, electronic business models penetrate into all spheres of human life, thus changing the conditions for the development of citizens, societies, as well as interstate associations in general. The electronic business is a theoretical, methodological and practical-applied form of an adequate response of the modern world to the corresponding post-industrial challenges [13, c. 2]. However, today in Ukrainian legal science issues of legal regulation of e-business in Ukraine are considered rather superficially. As a rule, conceptual developments regarding e-business are presented in economic science, science of public administration, etc.

With the help of the Internet it is possible to quickly and with little expense withdraw and promote products to national and international markets. Internet shops in Ukraine are at the stage of rapid development, since Internet commerce can significantly reduce the cost of products, as there is no need to maintain retail space, it is not necessary to keep sales staff [14, c. 79]. The expansion of electronic forms of business is the result of the socio-economic transformation of the conditions of the development and functioning of a modern post-industrial society, resulting in a radical shift of the market towards intangible assets (information, knowledge, intellectual property, rights and obligations, electronic services, software) [13, c. 9]. The further development of the information society on domestic spaces, the introduction and development of modern information and

communication technologies will enable the effective formation of the national model of electronic business, taking into account the existing positive experience of other countries in this area.

In this context, it is important to focus attention on the fact that, since the issues of economic development, granting of appropriate permits, etc. are at the disposal of public authorities, the integration and systematic updating of information and communication technologies in the work of public authorities and local self-government bodies is among the top priorities.

Considering a qualitatively new role of the economic system of society as an important element for building a modern social structure, we must realize that we are approaching fundamentally new forms of relations in which the approach to further use of property (the basis of the modern economic system) will be determined not by the status of individuals, but by the purpose for satisfaction of social needs.

New horizons of development are open to those states, where the social structure optimally promotes the realization of creative potential of citizens. Ensuring a decent place in the global coordinate system involves transforming the state into a truly innovative one, along with the bureaucracy reduction, increase in creative functions and the construction of a mechanism for virtually continuous participation of citizens in a social organization [15, c. 5]. Therefore, today human creativity in any sphere is an important component of the development of the social structure and its components, such as social and economic systems.

In a decentralized environment, self-organization of the public seems to be necessary, which will contribute to regional development.

After all, nowadays regional policy is focused not on the development of regions, but on their support, which does not contribute to the socio-economic uplift of the country. Therefore, regions need to make the transition to the formation and implementation of a self-development policy. This is especially important in the context of the limited economic, social, financial and other resources of the state, when the actual task is to introduce mechanisms for the effective use of socio-economic potential of regions on the basis of self-development [9]. This condition is associated with the lack of elaboration of mechanisms for regional and local self-development.

We emphasise that self-development of the region is a self-sufficient socio-economic development with adaptive properties for overcoming unfavorable social, economic and ecological tendencies and with the ability of the region to achieve balanced development, self-regulation, self-improvement with maximum use of internal reserves, as well as external borrowing resources to meet the needs of the population [9]. Self-development of the region involves the ability of authorized entities to determine the purpose and objectives correctly, their implementation in accordance with existing realities.

Conclusions. Summing up the theoretical and legal analysis of the social and economic systems of society as elements of the modern social structure, it is necessary to note the following.

1. The subject of scientific knowledge of the economic and social systems as elements of the modern social structure of Ukraine has a significant theoretical and applied role and focuses on the political and legal aspects of science in the theory of state and law and branch legal sciences. Knowledge of the economic and social components of the modern social structure is determined by the inadequate practice of their implementation. Modern economic and social systems of society are complex entities. The economic system of society is a coherent, normative and institutionalized arrangement of the interaction of various elements of economic activity aimed at the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of tangible and intangible goods, services, profit making in order to meet the needs and interests of people. The social system of society is defined as a coherent, complex and orderly interaction of social associations and individual entities of a general and specific nature.

2. Ensuring the citizens of Ukraine with the opportunity to fully implement economic and social rights requires the renewal of the economic system of society in the following areas: active introduction of innovative technologies; cooperation and attraction of international investors; promotion of the peoples creative potential; maximum supply of goods by the national market; transition to a system of export of end-use goods, not raw materials; balance of economic freedom; providing high-quality service. Their implementation requires the reform of domestic legislation, the detailed elaboration of a national mechanism for achieving

this, with the involvement of representatives of Ukrainian and foreign business.

3. Information and communication technologies have become the basis for the formation of a new type of economy – cybereconomy, due to the provision of unique opportunities in the field of the movement of capital, goods and services. The modern economic system of Ukrainian society is forced to adapt to information and computer reality. World trends make it necessary to carry out an

innovation restructuring of the domestic economic system of society, since today the absence of the specified significantly weakens the position of Ukraine and suspends its integration.

References:

1. Hrabynskiy I. M. Suchasni ekonomichni systemy: teksty leksii. Lviv, 1996 [in Ukrainian].
2. Havrylyshyn B. D. Do efektyvnykh suspilstvy: Dorohovkazy v maibutnie: dop. Rym. Klubovi [uporiad. V. Rubtsov]. 4-te ukr. vyd., bez zmin. Kyiv, 2013 [in Ukrainian].
3. Moiseienko K. Ye. Mekhanizm funktsionuvannia i rozvytku sotsialno-ekonomichnoi systemy suspilstva: dys. ... kand. ekon. nauk. 2015 [in Ukrainian].
4. Ekonomicheskaya teoriya: politekonomiya: uchebnik [V. D. Bazilevich, E. S. Bazilevich, N. I. Grazhevskaya]; pod red. V. D. Bazilevicha. Moskva: Kiev, 2009 [in Russian].
5. Pavlyishenko M. Ekonomicheskaya sistema ili sposob proizvodstva? *Ekonomika Ukrainyi*, 2000, 3, 63-72 [in Russian].
6. Pryor F.L. A Guidebook to the Comparative Study of Economic Systems. Englewood Cliffs. New York, 1985.
7. Nalyvaiko O. I., Chepik-Tregubenko O. Economic and Social Systems of Society as Elements of Social Structure: Concept, Objectives, Trends: collective monograph / Collective monograph: Challenges and prospects for the development of legal systems in Ukraine and EU countries: comparative analysis. Riga, 2019, Volume 1, 256-272.
8. Priieshkina O. Konstytutsiinyi lad ta ekonomichna systema: zahalnoteoretychni aspekty. *Yurydychnyi visnyk*, 2015, 1, 23-30 [in Ukrainian].
9. Sotsialno-ekonomichniy potentsial staloho rozvytku Ukrainy ta yii rehioniv: vektory realnoho postupu: natsionalna dopovid. Za red. E. M. Libanovoi, M. A. Khvesyka. Kyiv, 2017 [in Ukrainian].
10. Iohin V. Ya. Ekonomicheskaya teoriya: uchebnik. Moskva: Yurist', 2006 [in Russian].
11. Iefimenko S. A. Sotsialno-filosofski osnovy biznesu u konteksti suchasnoho hromadianskoho suspilstva: dys. ... kand. filos. nauk. Odesa, 2016, 14 [in Ukrainian].
12. Iefremova K. V. Derzhavna polityka ta elektronnyi biznes v Ukraini. *Pravo ta innovatsii*. 2015, 1, 50-54 [in Ukrainian].
13. Vorobiova O. P. Vprovadzhennia elektronnoho biznesu v Ukraini: derzhavno-upravlinskyi aspekt: avtoref. dys. ... kand. nauk z derzh. upr. Kyiv, 2013 [in Ukrainian].
14. Sytnyk I. P., Holovina A. V. Elektronnyi biznes i yoho rozvytok v Ukraini. *Molodyi vchenyi*, 2016, 2, 79-82 [in Ukrainian].
15. Lych V. M., Shediakov V. Ye. Udoskonalennia metodolohii doslidzhennia systemy ekonomichnykh vidnosyn u protsesi modernizatsii suspilstva. *Formuvannia rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukraini*, 2012, 9 [in Ukrainian].